

PRINCIPAL CLASSROOM VISITATION PRACTICE AND TEACHERS' TASK PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study was carried out mainly to find out the impact of principals' classroom visitation on teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design of correlational study was used for the study. The population for this study consisted 8,375 teachers and 209 principals. Validated instruments entitled, "Teachers' Task Performance Questionnaire" (TTPQ) and "Principals' Classroom Visitation Practice Questionnaire" (PCVPQ) were employed to collect data from the sample of 220 teachers and 80 principals. The sample for this study consisted 80 principals in which five principals were selected from each of the 16 Local Government Area of Ekiti State using, stratified simple random sampling technique and 220 teachers were selected proportionately because, the schools were not having equal number of teachers. The study revealed that the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation and the level of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State are relatively moderate; and that principals' classroom visitation made a significant contribution to the teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Principal, Classroom Visitation, Teachers' Task, Performance, Public Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' task performance could be referred to as the potential and ability of the teachers to apply instructional strategies and appropriate material as outlined in the scope and sequence of the selected curriculum to teaching and learning process. It also includes encouraging students' participation in the classroom, monitoring students' activities, well-organised lesson notes, good use of the academic curriculum for teaching, classroom control and management, fantastic instructing methods, monitoring of learners' activities, evaluation of learners' overall performance and so on. According to Owan (2018), the effectiveness with which a teacher carries out his or her pedagogical and instructional duties to foster student learning and the realisation of learning goal is what is termed "teacher task performance"

It has been observed by the researchers that most teachers in public secondary schools in Ekiti State are not so dedicated to their job; most of them are not interested in writing notes of lesson and even giving assignments to the pupils. More so, there have been reports of teachers wasting time in the staff common room when they are supposed to be in the classroom teaching. It has also been observed that some of the teachers do not often take time to explain his or her lesson until the students understand; maintain discipline in the classroom (classroom

management); make use of the right instructional materials while teaching; ensure students do effect corrections; cover syllabus on time before the end of the term; give and mark the students assignments regularly; strive to ensure that the students possess textbooks to aid learning and so on. That is why Stronge, Ward and Grant (2011) see a fantastic teacher as anyone who should be capable of using unique teaching techniques and understanding when and how to alternate from one teaching method to the other during lesson periods.

Classroom visitation is a method of school supervision in which the principal visits or observes the teachers' method of teaching, presentation of lesson, motivation of students for learning, assignments and use of teaching and learning aids. He or she observed also the discussion and verbal interaction in the classroom, student's interest and attention, and the classroom atmosphere in general. It is a type of visit that should be announced and should be followed by a conference, usually in the principal's office. Abebe (2014) examined classroom observation procedures at government secondary schools of Kamasi and found out that although supervisors carried out classroom visit, they would not arrange such visits with the teachers concerned. According to Iloh, Nwaham, Igbinedion and Ogogor (2016), classroom visitation or observation involves practicality in real classroom visitation whereby the supervisee presents what he or she had prepared for his or her lesson, utilising various teaching methodologies, instructional materials, interaction with the learners, jotting salient points on the instructional board, assessing the students using both formative and summative evaluations, coordinating class activities while the supervisor (the principal) inspects, observes and evaluates what and how the instructor has performed. However, it appears most of the principals in Ekiti State public secondary schools are no more engaging in most of the above characteristics of classroom visitation or observation which may result into low teacher task performance.

In a study conducted by Adegbesan (2008) on quality assurance in Vocational Technical Education curriculum implementation through effective classroom interaction analysis techniques found out that instructors' work performance has been declining in recent years, likely due to lack of frequent supervision; Maldrine and Kiplangat (2020) on relationship between supervision and job satisfaction among public secondary schools teachers in Nakuru West Sub-Country, Kenya found out that there was no correlation between how supervision interacts with employees and their level of job happiness; Edo and David (2019) on the influence of school supervision strategies on teachers' job performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria found out that both teachers and principals valued classroom visits and demonstrations as supervision tactics that aided teachers' performance in their job; Rashid (2001) on the perception of teachers about supervisory practices in Riyadh schools found out that classroom visitation enhances teachers task; Hussen (2015) on instructional supervisory approaches practiced in preparatory schools of Arsi zone, Ethiopia found out that classroom visitation was not frequently conducted by a majority of principals; Simbano (2013) on the influence of the principals' supervision functions on teachers' work performance in the Arusha Municipality, Tanzania found out that teachers benefit from principals' instructional supervision.

More so, Paul, David, Musaazi and Joseph (2016) conducted a study on instructional supervision and pedagogical practice of secondary school teachers in Uganda found out that supervision of teaching improves instruction but it was not adequately conducted in public secondary schools in Uganda; Garba, Waweru and Kaugi (2019) on principals' classroom visitation and its influence on teachers' pedagogical practices in public secondary schools in Bauchi State, Nigeria found out that principals' classroom visitation has a positive and statistically significant effect on pedagogical practices of teachers in public secondary schools in Bauchi State, Nigeria; Sule, Ameh and Egbai (2015) on supervisors' practices and teachers' effectiveness, found out that the competence level of teachers increases with classroom observation; Nnebedum and Akinfolarin (2017) on principals' supervisory techniques as correlates of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, found out that there is a high positive correlation between classroom observation technique; Walef, Nikmatulali, Marsidin and Rifma (2023) on implementation of the principal's supervision on teachers' performance, found out that the implementation of supervision of the school principal has not been carried out properly.

Theory X and Y

This theory was propounded by Douglas McGregor in 1960. He developed his idea of philosophies along with assumptions which emerge from these views of human nature.

Theory X: A work-Centred Approach

This theory was based on assumption preposition generally linked with the conventional or efficiency views of management. It can be argued that the principle underlying this theory is "the carrot and stick" The assumptions are:

- i. An average individual is naturally lazy and thus has an inherent dislike for work and will avoid it, if possible.
- ii. An average human being is dependent, unimaginative, and shortsighted. He therefore, must be controlled, and directed to achieve organisational objectives.
- iii. An average human being is irresponsible and therefore, needs to be coerced and even, threatened with punishment in order to achieve organisational goals.
- iv. An average man has fixed or set ways of doing things.
- v. An average individual is resistant or hostile to authority and leadership.
- vi. An average human being wishes to avoid responsibilities, has little ambition but above all, seeks security.

Theory Y: A people-centred Approach

This theory's assumption stand for a much more direct evaluation of human behaviour. It was not based on pessimistic philosophy but on optimistic philosophy about human nature. According to Sule, Arop and Alade (2012), McGregor's dissatisfaction with theory x management and its assumptions' failure to consider human needs that relate to self-fulfilment,

self-actualisation, ego satisfaction and the social needs of man led him to propound theory y. It can also be noted that this theory is the integration of personal and corporate objectives. The assumptions are:

- i. An average human being is naturally active and enterprising. The use of physical and mental efforts are as natural as play.
- ii. An average employee is independent, creative and grows on the job.
- iii. An average human being is loyal and related. Thus, external control and threat of punishment are not the only way of influencing behaviour.
- iv. People learn to exercise self-control, self-direction and optimum performance in the service of objectives to which they are committed.
- v. An average individual is capable of broad vision and long view.
- vi. An average man learns under encouraging and proper work condition as well as conducive environment. He is not only willing to accept responsibilities, he also seeks responsibilities.

To relate the above theories to the existing situational phenomena, one needs to note that as school heads struggle to accomplish the educational objectives of instruction, they tend to show behaviour in tandem with the assumptions of theory x and theory y as stated above. According to Peretomode (2001), school head who adopt the leadership style consisted with theory x are characterised by dictatorial procedures, eagerness for punitive measures against the subordinates and lack of participative management. He opined that the reason for theory x was a philosophy of direction, closer supervision, external control and authoritarian and directive style of leadership. This assertion implies that a school head who believes in theory x would always feel that an average employee has inherent dislike for work will avoid it, if possible and so must be forced to work.

Meanwhile, school head who make use of the leadership style incorporated in theory y are known for openness of communication with their subordinates, understanding and show interest in helping them to develop and note their potentials towards the accomplishment of same objectives. Peretomode (2001) still pointed out that school head who adopted theory y will encourage delegation of authority for many decisions to the subordinates; improve the free flow of information and communication within the organisation; recognise that people are motivated by complex set of psychological, not just money; and make an effort to make workers' jobless routine and boring. The above assertion implies that school head in this level believed that if work is satisfying, it is as natural as play and if well rewarded, it will make workers to have self-direction and self-control.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation?
2. What is the level of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between principal classroom visitation practice and teachers' task performance.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey and correlational research methods were used for this study. The population consisted 8, 375 teachers and 209 principals from 209 public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria (Source: Statistics Unit, Teaching Service Commission, Ekiti State, Nigeria). The sample for this study consisted 80 principals in which five principals were selected from each of the 16 Local Government Area of Ekiti State using stratified simple random sampling technique and 220 teachers who were selected proportionately because the schools were not having equal number of teachers. Two sets of instruments titled, Teachers' Task Performance Questionnaire (TTPQ) and Principals' Classroom Visitation Practice Questionnaire (PCVPQ) were used to collect data from the principals and teachers respectively for the study. The instruments were shown to specialists in the field of Tests and Measurement and Educational Management who checked and read the contents for adequate coverage of the topic and clarity of the items 1-12 for PCVQ and items 1-26 for TTPQ, for face and content validity. The reliability coefficient (r) calculated were 0.71 and 0.81 for PCVPQ and TTPQ respectively through test-re-test method, which was high enough to ensure the reliability of the instruments. The two sets of instrument were administered personally by the researchers. The hypothesis formulated was tested at a 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's product-moment correlation statistics.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation?

Table 1: The Extent To Which Principals In Public Secondary Schools In Ekiti State Make Use Of Classroom Visitation

Principals' use of classroom visitation	Frequency	Percentage
Low (12-16)	41	18.64
Moderate (17-32)	126	57.27
High (33-48)	53	24.09
Total	220	100.00

Table I shows the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation. The result shows that out of 220 teachers sampled, 41 teachers representing 18.64 percent responded to low extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation. Moreover, 126 teachers representing 57.27 percent responded to moderate extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation while those teachers who responded to high extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation were 53 representing 24.09 percent. This shows that the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation is relatively moderate.

Research Question 2: What is the level of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria?

Table 2: The Level of Teachers' Task Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Level of teachers' task performance	Frequency	Percentage
Low (26-37)	23	28.75
Moderate (38-69)	36	45.00
High (70-104)	21	26.25
Total	80	100.00

Table 2 shows the level of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The result shows that out of 80 principals sampled, 23 principals representing 28.75 percent responded to low level of teacher task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Moreover, 36 principals representing 45.00 percent responded to moderate level of teacher task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria while those principals who responded to high level of teacher task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria were 21 representing 26.25 percent. This shows that the level of teacher task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria is relatively moderate.

Research Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between principal classroom visitation practice and teacher task performance

Table 3: Test of Relationship between Principal Classroom Visitation Practice and Teacher Task Performance

	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Principal classroom visitation practice	300	12.34	2.87	0.53*	0.19
Teachers' task performance	300	80.44	7.34		

*p < 0.5 (significant result)

Table 3 shows that the r-calculated (0.53) is greater than the p-value (0.19) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is not accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between principal classroom visitation practice and teachers' task performance.

DISCUSSION

The result showed that the extent to which principals in public secondary schools in Ekiti State make use of classroom visitation was relatively moderate. This implies that the principals were not visiting the classroom to observe the teachers up to expectation. This might be as a result of the tight schedule of responsibilities of the principals. This finding agrees with that of Adegbesan (2008) who found out that instructors' work performance has been declining in recent years, likely due to lack of frequent supervision; Hussen (2015) who found out that classroom visitation was not frequently conducted by a majority of principals; Paul, David, Musaazi and Joseph (2016) who found out that supervision of teaching improves instruction but it was not adequately conducted in public secondary schools in Uganda; and, Walef, Nikmatulali, Marsidin and Rifma (2023) who found out that the implementation of supervision of the principal has not been carried out properly.

The result revealed that the level of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State was relatively moderate. This implies that teachers were not performing their tasks up to expectation. This might be because, the teachers were not dedicated to their job up to expectation. This finding agrees with that of Stronge, Ward and Grant (2011) who see a fantastic teacher as anyone who should be capable of using unique teaching techniques and understanding when and how to alternate from one teaching method to the other during lesson periods.

The study also revealed that there is a significant relationship between principal classroom visitation practice and teachers' task performance. This implies that principal classroom visitation practice enhances teacher task performance. This might be because of the principal's regular visits to the classroom to observe the teachers method of teaching, motivation of students for learning, use of teaching aids and so on. This finding agrees with that of Edo and David (2019) who found out that both teachers and principals valued classroom visits and demonstrations as supervision tactics that aided teachers' performance in their jobs; Rashid (2001) who found out that classroom visitation enhances teachers' task; Simbano (2013) who found out that teachers benefit from principals' instructional supervision; Sule, Ameh and Egbai (2015) who found out that the competence level of teachers increases with classroom observation; and, Nnebedum and Akinfolarin (2017) who found out that there is a high positive correlation between classroom observation technique and teachers job performance in secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. In contrast, Maldrine and Kiplangat (2020) found out that there was no correlation between how supervision interact with employees and their level of job happiness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was inferred that the principals were not visiting the classroom to observe the teachers up to expectation and that the teachers were not also performing their tasks up to expectation. It was also inferred that principal classroom visitation practice enhanced teachers' task performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. The principals should not relent on their efforts at visiting the classroom regularly to observe the teachers so that they can meet up to expectation.
2. The teachers should not also relent on their efforts at performing their tasks so that they can meet up to expectation.
3. The principals should try as much as possible to maintain and improve upon their classroom visitation practice by observing the teachers regularly.

Competing Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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